

UNDERSTANDING ACADEMIC SELF CONCEPT AND LOCUS OF CONTROL INRELATION TO SELF REGULATION AND SELF ESTEEM WITH THE HELP OF QUANTITATIVE RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Sneha Jadhav

Research Scholar,

University Of Mumbai

Research Guide: Dr. Judy Grace Andrews

Abstract

Achieving academic success is one of the important part of every students life. Academic success is not only related to scholastic abilities but also with the personality factors of the students including their academic self-concept, locus of control, self-esteem self-regulation. The current study has two fold aims. One is to understand academic self-concept, locus of control, self-esteem and self-regulation independently and two is to find out whether there exists any relationship between these variables amongst STD IX students from SSC and CBSC board aided as well as unaided schools students. The sample consisted of 1012 STD IX students from SSC and CBSC aided and unaided schools. In order to collect data academic self-concept scale by D'Souza (2006) to measure academic self-concept and the self-regulation questionnaire (SRQ) by Brown, Miller and Lawendowski (1999) to measure self-regulation were used. In order to collect data for locus of control Rooters Locus of Control Test (1954) was used, for Self-Esteem Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale (1965) was used .The result of the present study revealed that there is a significant positive correlation between academic self-concept and self-regulation and academic self-concept and self-esteem as well as significant negative correlation found between locus of control and self-esteem and locus of control and self-regulation amongst STD IX students belonging to SSC and CBSC aided and unaided schools. Also there was significant combined relationship found between academic self-concept, self-esteem and self-regulation and locus of

control, self-esteem and self-regulation.

Key words: *Academic Self-Concept, Locus of Control, Self-esteem, Self-regulation*

Introduction: *The purpose of education is to replace an empty mind with an open one.*

Malcom Forbes quote with his intuitive perspective has indeed given a thought provoking idea. Student's academic success is considered to be very important and essential in their lives. For their parents and for themselves too it becomes the most vital aspects of their lives.

Unfortunately most of the people in society try to link the academic success with only intelligence or students scholastic abilities. No doubt these abilities contribute majorly in their academic achievement but with these abilities some of the personality factors are also important.

Academic success is a combination of student's scholastic abilities and their personality traits. Some of the personality factors which will play a great role in their academic success are locus of control, self-esteem, and self-regulation.

These personality factors are not only significant for academic success but also for students overall growth and psychological well being. Such personality factors are studied by various researchers separately as well as with various other combinations as they are so important for everyone in the society in general.

These all complexities are getting recognized in the recent times by various researchers in the field of education. The current study intends to analyze the relationship between academic self- concept, locus of control, self-esteem and self-regulation considering three variables at a time with the help of multiple correlation of STD IX students. The paper confines itself to the city of Mumbai and Navi Mumbai.

Review of Related Literature

Academic self-concept

Jagpreet (2009) conducted a study to explore academic achievement and home environment as correlates of self-concept sample of 300 adolescents of ninth class from government and private schools of Patiala district of Punjab, through descriptive method of research. The study revealed a positive, yet non-significant correlation of self-concept with academic achievement and home environment among adolescents

Locus of control:

Das and Rathor (1989)³ studied locus of control and cheating behaviour in achieving

and non- achieving conditions, among students found that cheaters (externals) and non-cheaters (internals) differ in LOC scores in non- achieving conditions. In achieving conditions, cheaters are more external in comparison to non- cheaters. Non- cheaters, however, are internally oriented in both conditions.

Self-regulation

Ning H., Downing K. (2010) conducted research on the reciprocal relationship between motivation and self-regulation: A longitudinal study on academic performance. In this study researcher adopts the social cognitive perspective and examine the reciprocal interplay between motivation and self-regulation constructs (as measured by the Learning and Study Strategies Inventory) in influencing academic performance. The findings from this study have major implications for the importance placed on motivation and self-regulation as means of facilitating academic success.

Self-esteem:

Viale W., Patrick C. L., Ciarrochi J.(2010) studied the relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement is one that is regarded by many educators as a well-established fact. This belief has been often invoked in order to argue against the provision of ability grouping for gifted students. Refuting that commonly-held belief, this research examined the relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement in 65 high-ability secondary students, a sample drawn from a longitudinal study of over 900 students. The research demonstrated that there were no differences in measured self-esteem between the gifted and non-gifted students. More contentiously, though, the research found no correlation between self-esteem and academic achievement for the gifted group.

Statement Of The Problem

Understanding Academic Self Concept And Locus Of Control In Relation To Self Regulation And Self Esteem With The Help Of Quantitative Research Methodology

Operational Definitions Of The Term

Academic Self-Concept

Academic Self-Concept has been operationally defined as the relatively stable idea possessed by student based on a combination of judgments by self and “significant others”, concerning his/her behavior, strengths and weaknesses in academic domain.

Locus of Control

Refers to a students' perception of the factors responsible for their successes or failures and their generalized expectations concerning where control over subsequent events resides.'

Self-Esteem

Self-esteem has been operationally defined as student's sense of value or self-worth, or the extent to which they value, appreciate or like themselves.

Self-Regulation

Self-regulation has been operationally defined as a process whereby a student sets goals for their work and then attempt to monitor, regulate and control their cognition, emotions, motivation and actions.

Aim of The Study

Broad aim of the study is to understand academic self concept and locus of control in relation to self regulation and self esteem with the help of quantitative research methodology.

Objectives of the Study

1. To ascertain combined relationship between Academic Self-Concept, Self-Esteem and Self- Regulation
2. To ascertain combined relationship between Locus of control, Self-Esteem and Self-Regulation

THE NULL HYPOTHESES FOR THE STUDY

- There is no significant combined relationship between Academic Self-concept, Self-Regulation and Self-esteem
- There is no significant combined relationship between Locus of Control, Self-Regulation and Self-Esteem

Design of the Study

Design of the study includes methodology of the study, sampling techniques, sample and tools of the research.

Methodology of the study

The descriptive research method included under the quantitative paradigm has been used in the present research. The Creational descriptive method of type has been adopted in the present research.

Sampling techniques

For the purpose of the present study systematic random sampling technique has been adopted for selecting STD IX students.

Sample

The sample of the study consists of 1012 students of STD IX from the school in Greater Mumbai and Navi Mumbai.

Tools Of Research

Academic Self-Concept Scale (ASCS)

A readymade tool called the academic-self-concept scale, was used for measuring academic-self- concept among the secondary school students.

Locus of Control

For measuring locus of control Julian Rotter's Locus of control scale was used.

Self-Esteem

The test used for the current research was Rosenberg Self-Esteem scale.

Self-regulation

The Self-Regulation Questionnaire (SRQ; (Brown, Miller, & Lawendowski, 1999) was used in the current study.

Findings

There is significant combined relationship between academic self-concept, self- esteem and self-regulation of STD IX students from Greater Mumbai and Navi Mumbai.

Table 1

Hypothesis	Variables	LO C	SR	SE	Multiplier	P-value		los
						0.0 5	0.01	
There is no significant combined relationship between Academic Self concept, Self Regulation and Self Esteem	ASC	1	0.2	0.32	0.33	0.062	0.081	S
	SR	0.2	1	0.28				
	SE	0.32	0.28	1				

There is significant combined relationship between locus of control, self-esteem and self-regulation of STD IX students from Greater Mumbai and Navi Mumbai

Table 2

Hypothesis	Variables	LOC	SR	SE	Multiplier	P-value		los
						0.05	0.01	
There is no significant combined relationship between Locus of Control, Self Regulation and Self Esteem	SR	-0.13	1	0.28	0.13	0.062	0.081	S
	SE	-0.07	0.28	1				
	LOC	1	-0.13	-0.07				

Discussion

There is significant combined relationship between academic self-concept, self-esteem and self-regulation and locus of control, self-esteem and self regulation in STD XI students. This means that academic self-concept, self-esteem and self-regulation and locus of control, self-esteem and self-regulation are related to each other. This finding is similar to the study done by Boysan Murat and Kiral Erkan (2015)⁶. The study wanted to understand the relationship between procrastination and various personality traits like locus of control and self-esteem amongst young adults (162 females and 80 males). They found out that procrastination is related to locus of control and self-esteem and similar personality characteristics.

Personality is the dynamic concept where there will be various traits related to each other. The combination of these traits will make a complete personality of the person and will consequently affect various other aspects of one’s life. Locus of control which denotes to what extent one believes that he or she is responsible for the events occurring in his or her life and that he or she can shape his or her own life. So those who have internal locus of control believes that they are the master of their own lives and they can shape their lives in the direction they want whereas those who have external locus of control believe that their lives are controlled by the external factors which are beyond their control and they are helpless. So those who have internal locus of control are found to be high of self-esteem where they believe that they are worthy people to respect as well as they are found to be high on self-regulation which means that they

can control their thoughts, feelings and actions to achieve any goal they want. With these factors academic self-concept, self-esteem and self-regulation also are significantly associated with each other as per various researches in the field.

Conclusion

Comprehending and analyzing the relationship between locus of control, self-esteem and self-regulation can give a new insight towards an interdisciplinary relationship between education and psychology as both are significant faculties of Humanities. Both have their independent status but their combined effects are seen on student's academic achievement as well as their mental health. Thus towards a broad based, multifaceted and resilient society, we ought to strengthen and unite two rather than view them as mutually exclusive.

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